

Zenodo Repository - How to upload guidance

Zenodo Web link: <https://zenodo.org/>

2023 release features: <https://blog.zenodo.org/2023/10/13/2023-10-13-zenodo-rdm/>

Leibniz IOER Zenodo Community: https://zenodo.org/communities/ioer_dresden

Zenodo is a free-of-use general-purpose research output repository. It is designed for long-term archiving (at least 20 years). The Leibniz IOER Zenodo Community filters and curates the various Zenodo research outputs in a centralised way. It allows sharing Open Access research outputs with a persistent identifier (DOI).

What can be uploaded? E.g. Reports, preprint publications, documentation, general data, white papers, presentations, posters, software, algorithms, images, layouts, designs, etc.).

Important:

- Once an upload is published, it cannot be removed. It is persistently archived.
- However, the metadata can be changed and edited at any time.
- Each new version (upload) will obtain a new DOI.
- Zenodo always provides an overarching DOI that cites all the versions and always resolves the latest version by clicking on it.

Get started!

1

New upload

Drag and drop files

OR

Upload files

2

Select the community where you want to submit your record.

Select a community

Click on **Select a community**

Select a community

All

My communities

IOER

Type **IOER**

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)

The Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and R...

Organization

Owner

Select

Click **Select** to accept this Community

Click **NO** if you don't have a DOI. Otherwise, click **YES** to add the existing DOI for the upload. **Zenodo provides two DOIs**. One which belongs to the specific version, together with an overarching DOI number. For example, the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7112779 has the following overarching DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7112778. New versions generate a new DOI. The overarching DOI number always resolves the latest version.

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

Copy/paste your existing DOI here.

Get a DOI now!

Option to **reserve a DOI** before publishing it.

Reserve a DOI by pressing the button (so it can be included in files prior to upload). The DOI is registered when your upload is published.

Select the **upload type** (e.g. Data, Software, Presentation, Preprint etc.).

Resource type *

Fill in your upload title.

Title *

Additional title *

Type *

Language

Alternative title

Select language

Add titles or subtitles. You can set multiple languages to the titles or subtitles.

+ Add titles

Publication date *

2023-10-25

Set the publication date.

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators *

+ Add creator

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name * **Given names**

Identifiers
e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations
Search or create affiliation

Role
Select role

Add the upload Creators.

Search for your name, otherwise add it manually.

Add manually your Surname and name.

Add your ORCID or ISNI, GND identifier.

IMPORTANT: Search for IOER and our institution affiliation will appear.

Add your role.

Della Chiesa, Stefano¹

IMPORTANT: At the preview phase or once published, **click on show affiliations** and **check that the IOER affiliation appears with the ROR logo identifier.**

ROR Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

The screenshot shows a metadata editor interface. At the top, there is a 'Description' section with a rich text editor toolbar containing icons for Paragraph, Bold (B), Italic (I), Link, Bulleted List, Numbered List, Indent, Outdent, Quote, Undo, and Redo. Below the toolbar is a large empty text area. To the left of this area is a button labeled '+ Add description'. Below the description area is a 'Licenses' section with a dropdown menu currently set to 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International'. Below the dropdown are two buttons: '+ Add standard' and '+ Add custom'. Three orange callout boxes with white text and orange borders provide instructions: the top box points to the description text area and says 'Fill in a brief **description/abstract** of the upload.'; the middle box points to the '+ Add description' button and says 'Add an additional description if desired.'; the bottom box points to the license dropdown and says '**Open Access (CC BY) is the default publication license.** It means the upload is freely available and usable with the single constraint of crediting/citing/acknowledging the source. You can choose from other standard licenses or add a custom one. Please, be aware that only CC-BY and CC0 are considered Open Access.'

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Suggest from: All

Languages

Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
<input type="text" value="YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

You can add contributors with their affiliation, ORCID, Role, etc.

Add the necessary keywords. It helps find uploads and filter them (e.g. by a project).

Primary language of your document/upload.

Add if applicable date of Submission/Acceptance/Etc.

Add version by typing e.g. **v 1.0** or **Version 1.0** for the first version. Or **v 2.0** or **Version 2.0** for the second version. For minor changes you might adopt **v 1.1** or **Version 1.1**.

Funding

Zenodo lists a few major funding agencies. It is not a comprehensive list. If you find your funder add it and specify the grant number. You might select existing funding **or add your custom one.**

Awards

+ Add award + Add custom

Some uploads are related to others. For example, a publication is associated with a dataset, an algorithm, documentation, a report, a presentation, etc. You **enhance the visibility of all the research outputs by listing the corresponding identifier** (using its Persistent Identifier, e.g. DOI).

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Select relation...			

+ Add related work

Zenodo allows to list some references. Put the whole reference string.

References

Reference string *

+ Add reference

You can add the journal details. It is generally used when the upload is published on a journal. Zenodo allows to upload existing publication with their own DOI.

Journal

Title <input type="text"/> <small>Title of the journal on which the article was published</small>		ISSN <input type="text"/> <small>International Standard Serial Number</small>
Volume <input type="text"/>	Issue <input type="text"/>	Pages <input type="text"/>

Imprint

Book title <input type="text"/> <small>Title of the book or report which this upload is part of.</small>		ISBN <input type="text" value="e.g. 0-06-251587-X"/> <small>International Standard Book Number</small>
Place <input type="text" value="e.g. city, country"/> <small>Place where the imprint was published</small>	Pages <input type="text"/>	

Thesis

Awarding university

You can add Metadata info about a conference related to the upload. It is frequent when you upload a poster or conference presentation.

Conference

Title <input type="text"/>	Acronym <input type="text"/>
Place <input type="text"/> <small>Location where the conference took place.</small>	Dates <input type="text" value="e.g. 21-22 November 2022."/>
Website <input type="text"/>	
Session <input type="text" value="e.g. VI"/> <small>Session within the conference.</small>	Part <input type="text" value="e.g. 1"/> <small>Part within the session.</small>

Save the uploaded draft and, review it using the preview feature. If you are satisfied, click publish. **Be aware that published output cannot be undone or withdrawn.**

Draft ⓘ

Save draft Preview

Publish

Choose Restricted Access to set access and usage constraints conditions. Users can see only the metadata.

Visibility*

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Choose Embargoed Access to make the upload available after a specific date. Embargo is enabled by selecting restricted.

Delete

You can submit the upload to one or multiple Communities at the preview phase or once published. You can view any pending submission or manage them.

Communities

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

- + Submit to community
- 🗨 Pending submissions
- ⚙ Manage communities